

EFFECT OF CONSULTATIVE MANAGEMENT ON THE PERFORMANCE OF KENYATTA NATIONAL HOSPITAL IN NAIROBI CITY COUNTY, KENYA

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7148603>

Published Date: 05-October-2022

Abstract: The country's current economic and social situations have had a negative impact on the delivery of health care services. Employee empowerment is one of the key values, which strives to have the right people with the necessary talents and attitude, as well as financial sustainability. The Kenyatta National Hospital, however, continues to suffer from inefficiency, low service quality, and consumer dissatisfaction. Therefore, this study sought to investigate the influence on consultative management on performance of Kenyatta National Hospital in Nairobi City County, Kenya. This study employed a descriptive research design. Kenyatta National Hospital will serve as the unit of analysis, while 911 Kenyatta National Hospital personnel from ten departments served as the unit of observation. A stratified sample approach was used to divide respondents into departments to ensure that all instances are represented. A simple random selection process was used to choose the respondents. A total of 278 persons, or 30.5 percent of the total population, was sampled. To collect primary data, a questionnaire was employed. There was 28 Kenyatta National Hospital respondents in a pilot study who were not included in the final study. The researcher conducted a content validity test to check that the surveys are written in simple English and that the questions are understandable. The Cronbach alpha test was used to determine reliability. To evaluate quantitative data, descriptive statistics such as mean and standard deviation were used. The data that was examined was presented using tables and figures. Inferential statistics were also done using correlation analysis and multiple regression analysis because there were various explanatory variables in this study. The study found that consultative management had a positive and significant influence on Kenyatta National Hospital's performance in Nairobi City County, Kenya. The study concluded that the hospital had a very effective of implementation of consultative management strategy which improved their performance through openness/respect, sharing of information and suggestion plans. The study recommended that the hospital should be aware of its business environment. This entails conducting a critical analysis of both the internal and external business environments.

Keywords: Consultative management, Organizational performance.

1. INTRODUCTION

Employee participation refers to how employees are taking part in workplace decision-making when it comes to shared decisions (Irawanto, 2015). According to Park (2018), increasing employee engagement can help an organization function better, and management must have specialized tools to help employees participate more actively in this area. According to Park (2018), high-performing and efficient businesses have a culture that encourages employee participation, and efficiency is a metric that actions both proficiency and viability. Therefore, workers are bound to take part in dynamic cycles, for example, objective setting and critical thinking, leading to improved performance.

Organizations all around the world have devised many processes to increase performance at all levels, from functional to employee, until overall organizational performance is improved (Bhatti & Qureshi, 2017). In Pakistan, Khattak, Iqbal, and Khattak (2018) find that organizations that improve their employees' abilities and knowledge outperform their competitors. As a result, in order to perform well and compete with market trends, businesses employees at all levels must be involved in dynamic cycles by allocating powers and position to them, adjusting group based structures, and enhancing their employees' capabilities.

Employees must now be considered as major stakeholders in the corporation due to recent changes in how employees are managed in South African enterprises. Whenever workers in different areas of the planet are respected the main importance of competitive advantage, South Africa is still mired in a labor crisis characterized by strikes (Franca & Pahor, 2016). Employee engagement in job responsibilities has numerous elements, according to Robinso, Perryman, and Hayday (2017), but most importantly, participation indicates a good attitude toward a business. As a result, most South African companies see growing employee engagement opportunities as the most powerful conduit for improving organizational performance.

According to Kelemba, Chepkilot, and Zakayo (2017), enhancing staff participation is a long-term process that necessitates both management and employee initiative to improve the performance of Government Healthcare Institutions in Kenya. In addition, Kelemba, Chepkilot, and Zakayo (2017) note that to foster a feeling of having a place and possession among representatives, suggest that these wellbeing establishments' administration empower expanded laborer support in business related choices and the joining of worker points of view into authoritative approach, and that participative administration be re-imagined and appropriately applied to work on workers' comprehension and perceptions of the organization.

Employee engagement permits representatives to work on their capacities and affords them control over their positions, permitting them to cherish their work (Lytle & Timmerman, 2016). Employee involvement in dynamic has been distinguished as an administration way to deal with working on the performance of the organization by pursuing common ground between employees and management, according to Ojokuku and Sajuyigbe (2016). As a result, good involvement may be argued to create opportunities for employees to share information about consumers, solve problems, and generate new ideas.

Managers use consultation management providing data to workers, paying attention to them, and taking into account what they are talking about prior to deciding. Managers are demanding and considerate employee viewpoints before making decisions through consultation management (Yameen et al., 2015). Employee consultation, according to Ismail, Zainuddin, and Ibrahim (2018), entails finding acceptable solutions to challenges through a real exchange of ideas and information. Furthermore, Ismail, Zainuddin, and Ibrahim (2018) emphasize that the consultation does not deprive the administrator of the right to manage; management still has to make a final decision, but it places a responsibility on seeking and considering the views of employees before making decisions.

The main public referral, teaching, and research hospital in Kenya is Kenyatta National Hospital (KNH), which was established in 1901. On April 6, 1987, the government issued Legal Notice No. 109, transforming it into a state corporation. As stated in the Notice, the hospital's responsibilities include receiving patients on referral from other Kenyan and international hospitals and institutions and offering specialized health-care services, and to provide medical education facilities at the University of Nairobi's College of Health Sciences., to provide nursing medical training services and other health and other related services, and to participate as a national referral hospital.

The third Strategic Plan for Kenyatta National Hospital, 2013-2018, outlines the Hospital's plan of action. Legal Notice No. 109 of April 6, 1987 states that the Hospital's duties include conducting research, facilitating training, delivering specialized medical care, and taking part in national health planning. The Hospital created its Strategic Plan through a significant amount of broad participation. Throughout the process, interviews and consultations with staff, management, the board of directors, and external stakeholders were conducted. This Strategic Plan, in contrast to the previous two, was developed utilizing the Balanced Scorecard methodology. The method emphasizes an integrated set of metrics that link customer, financial, internal process, and staff performance on the long-term success of the company

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Strikes and slowdowns, a lack of equipment and appropriate infrastructure, and the lack of human resources are just a few of the problems facing the health sector is currently confronting (Agbozo, Owusu, & Atakorah, 2017). Public reforms have been implemented, according to Lufunyo (2018), to improve organizational performance, improve the efficacy and efficiency of service delivery, and make them more responsive to public needs. Despite the modifications, public hospitals

continue to have dismal outcomes. As a result, health-care systems will be unable to function effectively and efficiently unless highly motivated human resources are provided with a conducive environment in which to work.

According to Ngure (2018), Kenyatta National Hospital's (KNH) environment is ever-changing and offers fresh opportunities and difficulties. The country's current economic and social conditions have a detrimental effect on how well healthcare is provided. One of the core values is the empowerment of employees, which seeks to have the right individuals with the correct talents and attitude; and the achievement of long-term financial viability. Choge (2020) notes, however, a hostile work environment, a lack of specialized skills, and inadequate succession planning continue to make it difficult for KNH to provide quality healthcare, which has led to inefficiency, subpar service, and unsatisfied patients. Furthermore, Kenyatta National Hospital suffers from a severe scarcity of medical personnel, which affects practically every department. The majority of the hospital's human capital is employed in the private sector. The cost of providing medical services rises as a result of specialist competition. Due to the problems, inadequate service preparation, reduced health worker productivity, and brain drain occur, with skilled and experienced healthcare professionals seeking better paying employment in the private sector and overseas.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Theoretical Literature Review

Fayol made a theoretical project in 1949 trying to come up with a more realistic and effective way to build an organization. It strives for clarity of administrative structure, legitimacy, class division, and the transfer of power to different employees depending on their personalities. According to the legal process, a company must have a well-established executive committee that defines the various positions and functions of employees. The progression of power and the extent of the work expected by the not entirely settled by the clearness of the administration lines. The issue of division of work mirrors the way that a reasonable division of work is utilized to advance the uniqueness and efficiency of every unit to accomplish the goals of the organization. In short, management theoretical experts have seen the benefits of productivity with ground-based supervision.

To additional this hypothesis, Fayol (1909) added to the extra standards of this reality. He fostered the scalar idea, which was opposed to the hierarchical structure to control administrative functions. Fayol (1909) goes on to say that extraordinary principles encouraged subordinates to deal with common concerns while managers deal with unfamiliar matters. The era of control concept states that a manager or the supervisor should not have more subordinates than they are capable of managing or screening, while the rule of departmental practice is that connected capacities ought to be isolated into discrete administration units. The truth of the solidarity of the request was additionally integrated into the development of professionalism.

This theory supports operational flexibility by demonstrating that the clarity of the line of management contributes to the progression of force and extent of work expected of every person, considering ceaseless observing and extra hierarchical execution with a particular objective. Management theory tries to devise a clever plan for setting up the entire organization. Theory recommends a well-organized management structure, a distinct division of labor, and the delegation of power and authority to managers in accordance with their areas of responsibility.

Empirical Literature Review

The impact of consultative management on corporate governance and corporate governance in the Egyptian banking sector was studied by Dajani and Zaki (2015). This was a pilot study aimed at identifying key drivers for consulting workers in Egypt. A list of research questions was developed and validated. The proposed organizations were predicted and described using retrospective analysis. Employee consultative management has a big impact on job performance, but not so much on company performance.

The impact of consultative management on the decision-making process of selected small and medium-sized firms in Lagos, Nigeria was investigated by Ojokuku and Sajuyigbe (2014). A questionnaire was used to gather information from 27 owners and managers and 119 employees of randomly chosen SMEs. Mathematical techniques that are both descriptive and non-descriptive were used to statistically analyze the collected data. The results showed that management of staff consultation in decision-making significantly impacted organizational performance in SMEs.

The influence of consultative management on organizational performance of Government Health Care Institutions in Kenya was investigated by Kuria, Namusonge, and Iravo (2016). The investigation was conducted using a descriptive survey

design. A total of 384 staff members at Kiambu and Machakos Level 5 Hospitals, as well as Kenyatta National Hospital, have been chosen to participate in the study by providing various samples. As a means of gathering data, questionnaires and interview guidelines were employed. Kenyan researchers found that consulting enhanced organizational performance.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study employed a descriptive research design. Kenyatta National Hospital will serve as the unit of analysis, while 911 Kenyatta National Hospital personnel from ten departments served as the unit of observation. A stratified sample approach was used to divide respondents into departments to ensure that all instances are represented. A simple random selection process was used to choose the respondents. A total of 278 persons, or 30.5 percent of the total population, was sampled. To collect primary data, a questionnaire was employed. There was 28 Kenyatta National Hospital respondents in a pilot study who were not included in the final study. The researcher conducted a content validity test to check that the surveys are written in simple English and that the questions are understandable. The Cronbach alpha test was used to determine reliability. To evaluate quantitative data, descriptive statistics such as mean and standard deviation were used. The data that was examined was presented using tables and figures. Inferential statistics were also done using correlation analysis and multiple regression analysis because there were various explanatory variables in this study.

4. FINDINGS

The study sought to determine the impact of consultative management on Kenyatta National Hospital's performance in Nairobi City County, Kenya. Table 1 gives the descriptive statistics.

Table 1: Consultative Management

Statements	Mean	Standard Deviation
Managers' openness at KNH empowers employees to be creative and give their opinions as they feel more respected and trusted	4.08	0.92
In this hospital there exists information sharing during meetings with my supervisor	4.05	0.95
Employees who take ownership of their responsibilities are more motivated as they are able to develop ideas and get feedback on their effort	4.30	0.70
Embracing an employee ownership-type mentality leads to improved communication and greater collaboration among employees and leaders	4.12	0.88
Employees can attain their maximum potential with the help of mentoring, which promotes their personal and professional development in a positive way..	3.21	1.79
Mentorship improves present and future managers' leadership and coaching abilities..	4.55	0.45

The statement that was strongly supported by the respondents included; mentorship improves present and future managers' leadership and coaching abilities (M=4.55, SD=0.45). This is in line with research done by Ojokuku and Sajuyigbe (2014), who examined how consultative management affected the decision-making process in a sample of small and medium-sized businesses in Lagos, Nigeria. They found that overall, staff consultation management in decision-making had a significant impact on organizational performance in SMEs.

The respondents agreed on the statements that employees who take ownership of their responsibilities are more motivated as they are able to develop ideas and get feedback on their effort (M=4.30, SD=0.70), embracing an employee ownership-type mentality leads to improved communication and greater collaboration among employees and leaders (M=4.12, SD=0.88), managers' openness at KNH empowers employees to be creative and give their opinions as they feel more respected and trusted (M=4.08, SD=0.92) and that in this hospital there exists information sharing during meetings with my supervisor (M=4.05, SD=0.95). This is in line with Kuria, Namusonge, and Iravo (2016) investigated the impact of consultative management on organizational performance of Kenyan Government Health Care Institutions and discovered that consultation improved organizational performance.

The respondents indicated to a moderate extent that employees can reach their full potential with the aid of mentoring, which positively fosters their professional and personal development. (M=3.21, SD=1.79). The finding contradicts the

findings of Dajani and Zaki (2015) research into the effects of consultative management on corporate governance and corporate governance in the Egyptian banking sector which found that employee consultative management has a significant impact on job performance but not as much on company performance.

Results of Inferential Statistics

Correlation analysis

Table 2: Correlation Analysis

		Consultative management	Organizational performance
Consultative management	Pearson Correlation	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)		
	N	271	
Organizational performance	Pearson Correlation	.641**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.002	
	N	271	271

The results in Table 2 show that consultative management had a strong relationship with organizational performance with Pearson r values of 0.641. This means that an improvement in consultative management would lead to improved performance of Kenyatta National Hospital.

Results of Regression Analysis

The extent to which consultative management influenced the performance of Kenyatta National Hospital was determined using regression analysis.

Table 3: Model Summary

Model	R	R square	Adjusted R square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.709 ^a	0.556	0.551	1.009

According to Table 3's findings, there was a variation in Kenyatta National Hospital's performance of 55.1%, or 0.551, at the 95% confidence level, as a result of changes in consultative management. Additionally, this implies that 44.9% of Kenyatta National Hospital performance is influenced by variables not examined in this study.

Table 4: Analysis of Variance

Model		Sum of squares	df	Mean square	F.	Sig.
1	Regression	83.609	1	83.609	381.776	.000
	Residual	59.302	270	0.219		
	Total	142.911	271			

The result as presented in Table 4 is that value of F (381.776) was greater than the value of Mean square value (83.609). In addition, the level of significance level obtained was less than 0.05 at 0.000. Therefore, this shows that there was a good fit of the model significantly predicting the performance of Kenyatta National hospital.

Table 5: Coefficient

		Unstandardised coefficients		Unstandardised coefficients		
		B	Sd.Err	Beta	t	Sig.
Model	(Constant)	.887	.210		4.219	.000
1	Consultative management	.783	.045	0.765	17.248	.000

The results as illustrated in Table 5 indicate that if the consultative management is held constant, the performance of Kenyatta National hospital would be at 0.887. The results also indicates that the core competence had a coefficient of 0.783 implying that the performance of Kenyatta National hospital would increase by a factor of 0.783 when consultative management is increased by one unit. The following is the expression of the resulting regression equation Performance of Kenyatta National hospital = .887 + 0.783 consultative management

In addition, that study found that the t-value was positive at 17.248 with a level of significance less than 0.05 at 0.000. This implied that consultative management had a significant prediction on the Performance of Kenyatta National hospital.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The study concluded that the hospital had a very effective of implementation of consultative management strategy which improved their performance through openness/respect, sharing of information and suggestion plans. The hospital improved its performance due to having an effective mentorship and coaching programs thus empowering their employees. KNH enabled the employees to enjoy autonomy within their workplace and creativity that greatly motivated their employees to lay their loyalty at the organization thus improving overall performance.

6. RECOMMENDATIONS

The research suggested that the hospital should be aware of its business environment. This entails conducting a critical analysis of both the internal and external business environments. By comprehending how the issue affects each stakeholder and how potential solutions might affect them as well, one can define their customers and their needs. The hospital administration must discover what its employees value most and genuinely honor those values to the best of its ability within budgetary and other constraints.

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